

**Trade and Policy Shocks in Nepal amid the Covid-19
Pandemic:
*Observations, Lessons and the Way Forward***

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Abstract

This paper examines the impact of COVID-19, anti-COVID-19 policy, and compensatory policy on the national economy, particularly on foreign trade based on secondary data of the daily database of COVID through descriptive statistics and regression models. The paper finds a result that COVID-19 infected 44.8 million populations and killed 1.2 million people of 215 countries of the world and 0.165 million affected people, 887 death tolls, per day new cases >3000 and recovery rate >74 percent from March 23, 2020, to September 30, 2020, in Nepal. Similarly, its anti-COVID policy's impact (0.86) is more severe than COVID-19 (0.44) in the economy. Its output is most vulnerable to trade: Indo-Nepal and Sino-Nepal. Finally, the compensatory policy is a stable shock to the negative consequence of COVID-19 and anti-COVID-19 policy. Therefore, the foreign trade sector is most vulnerable in Nepal. For survival, stable and stimulus of national economy and trade, the compensatory policy should be implemented.

Keywords: COVID-19, Trade, Export, Import, Trade Openness, Nepal

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Introduction

Foreign Trade as an external sector in the nation has a huge potential key driver of economic growth rate, income equity, and poverty reduction. Since the 1990s, South Asia has been struggling with trade gain from *internationalism* and *regionalism* through building a *liberal trade policy regime*. South Asian Preferential Trade Arrangement (SAPTA) to South Asian Free Trade Area (SAFTA) is an example of intra- and inter-regionalism within the South Asian Association of Regional Cooperation (SAARC) to improve trade share to US\$ 42 trillion international trades and to catch up to 7% of Global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) in SAARC through preferential trade and lowering of tariffs.

However, empirical and theoretical literature shows less than 5% intra-regional trade in the mutual trust deficit induced tariff and non-tariff barriers and protectionism, no trustworthiness of trade flows, higher cost of connectivity, and no strong trade bonding although multilateralism and regionalism have triggered to improve value and volume of trade of SAARC member countries. Its output is negligible trade outcomes to developing and least developing member countries in SAARC but the growth of trade dependency is interestingly impressive. An example is Nepal.

In Nepal, about 6.5% average growth miracle was recorded in the last three consecutive years from 2016, 2017, and 2019 (Asian Development Bank (ADB), 2019, World Bank (WB), 2019 & Ministry of Finance (MoF), 2020). Such appreciative miracles have bounced back with the desired growth confidence and hope triggered in the economy for achieving the national development goal of *happy Nepali, prosperous Nepal* within the next 20 years. It was a surprise in the mathematics of growth economics. Its reasons were underperformance of agricultural growth, industrial growth, and imbalance growth of trade sector

but over the performance of remittances led household consumption (29% of GDP).

However, the validity and significance of these pillars could not be ignored. Therefore, the uncontrolled growth of import trade that led to the trade imbalance has had mixed outcomes in the national economy. In macroeconomy, it is the unstable creator with the 1300 billion rupees trade deficit as the cost of export trade but the import of raw materials and capital goods and services have positive outcomes to strengthen and expands the productive sectors and construction of big projects: hydro and road and to create employment opportunities, resources, and products.

The trade of Nepal is still a magic box of a paradox between expectation and reality. In 2020, the trade-GDP ratio was 52% out of which the export GDP ratio was 9.8% meanwhile the import GDP ratio is 42%. As a result, the import-GDP ratio is excessive to the export-GDP ratio. In other words, the trade deficit-GDP ratio is 32.2%. It is greater than the remittance-GDP ratio (29%). In the figure, trade volume is recorded at Rs. 1992 billion. (MoF, 2020). In the trade statistics, Nepal has traded with 119 countries of the world out of which the trade statistics indicate 20 countries as major trade partners.

Despite 20 major trade partners, Indo-Nepal and Sino-Nepal trade are dominants with 65% and less than 5%, respectively in the trade structure. As a result, trade openness and liberalisation have not improved trade diversification and benefits as the target goal of Trade Policy 1996 and 2009 and National Five Years Plans (Ministry of Industry and Trade (MoIT), 1996, MoIT, 2009 and National Planning Commission (NPC), 2019). Its evidence is a huge trade deficit figure and rule in the trade.

In simple terms, import shares 94% and export shares only 6%. It indicates the growth of trade dependency and the degrowth of trade independence and the lower elasticity of export trade. Its result is 32% of the trade deficit-GDP, out of which the

Indo-Nepal trade deficit is 21% and then the rest is 11%. Similarly, the figure of export-import ratio shows 1:16 in the case of Indo-Nepal trade and 1:44 in the case of Sino-Nepal. Content analysis in import and export shows a higher variation of values between exported items and imported items. Nepal traditionally exports unprocessed agro products and handicrafts (cardamom, jute goods, textile, polyester, handicrafts, and juice) having low value, low competitive capacity, and low quantities.

Meanwhile, import content is essential, and industrial finished products: petroleum products, vehicles, machinery, electronics goods, medicines, etc. having high value and in large quantities. Such a trade deficit is due to the poor trade openness of both countries, India and China to Nepal, although they have provided Nepal a preferential treatment. Therefore, trade openness and liberalization have deepened the crisis of trade deficit, trade dependency, and domestic productivity. However, its inclusiveness is mentioned in the economic growth of the country, despite its 1.42 trade multiplier.

It does not mean a protective trade policy, regime, and philosophy. The reflection of ancient and medieval outward trade policy, regime, and philosophy can be found during the regime of the first Rana Prime Minister (PM) Jung Bahadur Rana. Then, Nepal adopted trade openness to foreign products and services in the domestic market (Bista, 2016). In the period from 1960 to 1980, import trade was restricted from tariff and non-tariff barriers (higher tariff, quota, and high subsidy) to protect the domestic industries and to generate revenue resources for development and regular expenditure in the narrow tax base and lower tax elasticity and buoyancy. Its side effect was a macro-economic crisis with a 5% current account deficit, 10.7% budget deficit, and 13% inflation in the 1980s (Bista, 2016).

Nepal had a question of stability and growth. The World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) had recommended Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) to liberalize

the Nepalese economy. As a result, trade liberalization policy would be executed to some extent. Its full-fledged liberalization was implemented in the 1990s after the effects of SAP II. As a follow-up, SAPTA-SAFTA was signed in 1993 for regionalism.

It was supplemented by the Gajural Doctrine in 1996 with the unilateral preferential concession to neighboring countries in trade. Its reflection in trade policy, regime, and philosophy can be found to date. In recent years, it is a curiosity whether trade liberalization has become counterproductive to the landlocked country Nepal in the growth of trade deficit, trade dependency, and contraction of productivity and production or whether trade leakages gravity in Indo-Nepal trade is an unexpectedly heavy load in such the growth of trade deficit.

Since the lockdown policy as a powerful anti-COVID-19 measure was state induced during the pandemic period to reduce its rapid and wider transmission from individual to the family and then the community, its strictness to shield international border and halting of transportation system affected all economic sectors but trade sector was considered unexpectedly extremely broken (MoF, 2020). By and large, deduction of the external sector in the four sector economies had made all economies closed and isolated undesired, and unplanned for the short run. It was looked like what classical economists mentioned as self-sufficient economies in the ancient and medieval periods. Thus, the trade sector was fully and partially halted in the world.

Nepal has endorsed anti-COVID-19 measures: hard and soft. In hard measure, a strict lockdown measure was executed from March 23 to July 21, 2020, to reduce the inflow of COVID-19 along with human mobility and goods flow. The Indo-Nepal and Sino-Nepal borders and transportation were closed down for two months. Then, the lockdown was internally removed with restrictions but both borders remained closed.

Again, the lockdown was formally announced by the government of Nepal from August 16 to September 7, 2020, when

it found the higher penetration growth per day of COVID-19 in the Kathmandu Valley. On September 7, it was lifted. Some soft measures were enforced, for example, odd-even number system and social distancing for transportation, the opening of cargo of raw materials, essential goods, and capital goods in trade but restricted to the flow of people, closure of schools and colleges with a focus on virtual education and closure of temples and restrictions on public gatherings.

It is argued that the strict lockdowns during the COVID-19 will have severe impacts on trade sectors. There were assumptions as follows: a) the lockdown would stop transportation system within the country and Indo-Nepal and Sino-Nepal trade transit; b) the flow of goods and services in import and export would be stopped; c) the export-import ratio in Indo-Nepal and Sino-Nepal would decline; d) the growth of trade deficit pressure would be unexpectedly lower; f) the capital account would be positive; g) macroeconomic stability would be improved as expected and; h) agriculture productivity and production would be better. Therefore, this study is relevant to test the above assumptions.

The study would examine mainly two issues: whether the impact of COVID-19 pandemic shock and anti-COVID-19 policy measures on the trade of Nepal will be wider and whether the compensatory policy tools to survival stabilize and stimulate the slowdown trade sector will be positive. Its output would be valuable to understand COVID-19, anti-COVID-19 Policy, and trade sector relationship and explore compensatory policy to trade sector. It would be valuable kinds of literature for academicians and policymakers to discourse seriously and sensitively on the trade sector to reshape and remake its exogenous crisis resilience and survival.

Objectives and Methods

Objectives

The paper examines the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic and anti-COVID-19 policy on the trade of Nepal. Its specific objectives are a) to assess the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the trade of Nepal, b) to examine the effect of anti-COVID-19 policy measures on the trade of Nepal, and c) to find out the compensatory policy tools to survive, stabilize and stimulate the slowdown trade sector.

Data and Methods

Let us suppose GDP is “Y” and COVID-19 positive cases. Let’s assume COVID-19 positive cases and anti-COVID-19 policy makes slow down GDP growth. Let us expand in the regression model as follows:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha + \beta X_{it} + \beta_1 D_{it} + \varepsilon \dots \dots \dots (i)$$

Where, α = intercept, β = coefficient of COVID-19 positive cases (X_{it}), β_1 = coefficient of Lockdown and border closure (D_{it}), ε = error term, X_{it} = COVID-19 positive cases, D_{it} = Lockdown and border closure,

Where, α , β , & β_1 are parameters and have $\alpha > 1$, $0 < \beta_1 < 1$ and $0 < \beta_2 < 1$.

This paper used secondary data sets of COVID-19. It includes COVID-19 positive cases and lockdown and border closure across the country from March 2020 to September 2020 collected from the website of the World Health Organization (WHO), along with the case of Nepal and South Asia. Its supplementary data sets related to Nepal were accumulated from Nepalese Government

agencies: Ministry of Finance, Nepal Government, and National Planning Commission, Nepal Rashtriya Bank, and Central Bureau of Statistics.

The analytical tool was SPSS to operate simple regression to estimate coefficient.

Figure 1: COVID pandemic in the World

Results and Discussions

Result I: COVID-19 Scenario in the World

Since its outbreak with 44 COVID-19 positive cases in Wuhan City of China on January 9, 2020 (WHO, 2020) with its first report on 31st December 2019 from Wuhan, China (Isaifan, 2020; Dutheil et al., 2020 and Han et al., 2020), till date, it has badly captured more than 210 countries across the world with the result of 5.2 million population positive cases, 0.4 million death and more than 0.2 million recovered (WHO, 2020). Horizontally and vertically, it badly impacted the public health system of the world by disclosing its advanced technology, services supply, and deliveries and its standards, along with insufficient beds, testing kits, and medicines (Huang et al., 2020, Kambalagere, 2020, Sohrabi et al., 2020 and Zhang et al., 2020).

In the United States (US), overwhelming COVID-19 positive cases could not get beds in the hospitals. A large number of patients were waiting for hospital beds and treatments. Similar constraints were found in Italy, Spain, UK, France, Germany, etc. (WHO, 2020). Besides, it has induced humanitarian, cultural, and religious crises. Christian community followed cremating the dead body instead of burial. Social distancing was maintained in funeral ceremonies. In Spain, the over flooding of dead bodies raised a demand for coffin and others. In Guatemala, dead bodies were being left a long week in the street (WHO, 2020). Dead bodies were buried *en masse* in New York. Thus, COVID-19 has been an undesired threat to the health of the population in the world.

Figures 1 & 2 show the higher growth of its density and gravity in developed countries from June 2020 to September 2020. For example, USA, Spain, Italy, France, Germany, and UK in June 2020.

Figure 1: COVID Scenario (June 20)

Source: Ministry of Health (MoH, 2020)

Figure 2: COVID Scenario (Sept 30)

Source: Ministry of Health (MoH), 2020

In September 2020, the US, India and Brazil, Russia, Spain, France, and the United Kingdom (UK) led in the COVID-19 fact sheet. Over time, its growth was faster than our expectations. Therefore, IMF and the World Bank (2020) projected a US\$ 3 trillion loss and recession as its cost with the growth of more than 50% unemployed populations and the growth of more than 50% poverty and vulnerability. Further, OXFAM (2020) predicted its distribution of intensity will be more in developing and least developing countries of Africa and Asia (OXFAM, 2020).

COVID-19 in South Asia

WHO (2020) showed the threat of COVID-19 pandemic in South Asia with the second rank of India. Figure 4 shows all countries in the COVID-19 pandemic exposure and vulnerability. However,

India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Afghanistan, and Nepal were at greater risk but Sri Lanka, Maldives, and Bhutan were in a controlled situation.

Figure 3: COVID-19 Status in SAARC Countries in 2020

Comparison	COVID - 19 in SAARC Countries			
	14 April 2020		29 Aug 2020	
Countries	Infected	Death	Infected	Death
India	10,541	358	3,539,712	63,657
Pakistan	5,716	96	295,372	6,284
Bangladesh	1,012	46	308,925	4,206
Afghanistan	714	23	38,143	1,402
Sri Lanka	218	7	2,995	12
Maldives	20	-	7,578	28
Nepal	16	-	37,340	207
Bhutan	5	-	195	-

Source: SAARC, 2020

As per the effectiveness of anti-COVID-19 measures in SAARC countries, its risk and vulnerability levels were heterogeneous.

COVID-19 in Nepal

Nepal was not free from COVID-19, although the cases were sluggish and negligible from March 23 to July 21, 2020. Figure 5 shows its fast growth from May 25, 2020, when labor migrants started to return from India, China, Saudi Arabia, Malaysia, etc. (WHO, 2020). Then, its trend rocketed with geometric growth. In September 2020, it reached 77817 cases, despite lockdown measures. Thus, Nepal was highly vulnerable.

Figure 4: COVID-19 Status in Nepal in 2020

Source: Ministry of Health (MoH), 2020

Figure 5: COVID19: Case, Recovery & Death

Source: Ministry of Health (MoH), 2020

In this scenario, there were three output indicators: COVID-19 cases, death, and recovery. Figure 6 presents a lower death rate but COVID-19 cases were dominant during lockdowns I and II but an 80% recovery rate provided comfort in the crisis.

Result II: COVID-19 pandemic and Trade

COVID-19 pandemic had direct and indirect effects. Besides, the effects of strict lockdown and border closures as anti-COVID-19 measures were expected, it had negative outcomes at macro and microeconomic level including economic growth, employment, sector output and performance, trade and balance of payment (BOP), fiscal deficit, livelihood, poverty, etc. Figure 7 shows the contraction of transport and communication by -13.25% and then -7.16% contraction of trade in comparison with the pre-COVID-19 scenario (MOF, 2020). It was followed by hotel/restaurant, government service, and industry. Thus, the overall economy was in a slowdown.

Figure 6: Trade Performance in pre and post COVID

Source: Ministry of Finance (MoF), 2020

Figure 8 shows the huge contraction of import and export trade with India and China from the pre-COVID-19 scenario. In the pre-COVID-19, the export and import ratio was 1:14 in Indo-Nepal trade and 1: 44 in Sino-Nepal trade. After COVID-19, its ratio sharply fell in both cases of import trade. In Indo-Nepal trade, it was 1:8.8 (Figure 9). Its implication was the fall of the trade deficit to Rs. 967.7 billion from Rs. 1161.2 billion.

In Sino-Nepal trade, it felt with Rs. 40 billion, meanwhile in Indo-Nepal trade, it was Rs. 100 billion. Despite its negative implications on the sector and aggregate economy, its positive implication was softer trade deficit pressure to a current account and capital account and then on the BOP. Similarly, other SAARC countries, Nepal got a positive BOP leading to improving macroeconomic stability but having negative economic growth (Figure 10).

Figure 7: Trade and COVID-19

Source: Ministry of Finance (MoF), 2020

Figure 8: Foreign Trade Balance of Nepal

Foreign Trade Balance of Nepal					In Billion Rs.
	Total Exports	Total Imports	Total Trade	Trade Deficit	Export: Import Ratio
F.Y. 2075/76 (2018/19) Shrawan-Bhadra	14.70	232.35	247.05	217.65	1: 15.8
Share % in Total Trade	6.0	94.0			
F.Y. 2076/77 (2019/20) Shrawan-Bhadra	18.50	229.50	248.00	211.00	1: 12.4
Share % in Total Trade	7.5	92.5			
F.Y. 2077/78 (2020/21) Shrawan-Bhadra	20.44	178.85	199.29	158.41	1: 8.8
Share % in Total Trade	10.3	89.7			
Percentage Change in First Two Month of F.Y. 2076/77 compared to same period of the previous year	25.9	-1.2	0.4	-3.1	
Percentage Change in First Two Month of F.Y. 2077/78 compared to same period of the previous year	10.5	-22.1	-19.6	-24.9	

Source: Ministry of Finance (MoF), 2020

Figure 9: Negative Economic Growth of Nepal

Source: Ministry of Finance (MoF), 2020 and Ministry of Health (MoH), 2020

It can be observed that:

- A big threat was the open border that induced unauthorized and informal Indo-Nepal trade, which was sharply falling during the Indo-Nepal border closures and closures of transportation and communication.

- Black markets and smuggling markets were temporarily closed down but their benefit could not be seen in informal trade, custom revenue, and fair market competition.
- Crime rates related to unauthorized and informal trade fell in Indo-Nepal border markets and settlements.

Result III: Impact of anti-COVID-19 measures on Economy and Trade

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation). In column 1, three variables are GDP(Y) as dependent variable and COVID-19 (x) and Lockdown and border closure (D) measures as independent variables. Standard deviations of these variables are so far significant from the mean, except lockdown and border closure.

Table 1

Variable	Mean (Standard Deviation)
GDP (Y)	3.4906E3(175.20)
COVID-19 (x)	98.2727 (101.48)
Lockdown & border closure (D1)	2.9765E2(162.26)

Table 2 presents the results of a simple multiple regression model in which the dependent variable is GDP(Y) and two independent variables are COVID-19(X) and lockdown and border closure (D) having two parameters: β and β_1 . In the results of the regression model, parameter (β) explains the marginal change of COVID-19 cases (x) i.e. change in GDP and change in COVID-19 cases ratio. In other words, change COVID-19 explains to change 1 percent of GDP. Similarly, parameter (β_1) explains whether 1% change in GDP will be in a lockdown and border closure or not.

Considering the above results of the econometric model, they provide sufficient evidence on the share of independent variables: COVID-19 (x) and lockdown and border closure (D) in GDP. To minimize the undesired threat of the COVID-19 pandemic and its fast transmission rate, the national economy i.e. real GDP(Y) was directly and indirectly derailed by the COVID-19 pandemic and anti-COVID-19 policy measures.

In the model, the p-value of these two independent variables shows significant and valid. Parameter (β) of COVID-19 shows a negative sign with 0.44 values and parameter (β_1) of lockdown and border closure shows a negative sign of 0.86. In the result of the model, R^2 is 0.99. It explains the dependent variable GDP(Y) by 99% from independent variables: COVID-19 (x) and lockdown and border closure (D).

Table 2

Dependent variable: Average Real GDP(Y)			
Regressor	1	2	3
Constant	3787.3 (4.5)		
COVID-19 (X)		- 0.407(0.033)	
Lockdown & Border closure (D)			-0.86(0.021)
Observations	44		
Overall R2	0.99		
Note:			
* is <5 percent of P-value.			
Dependent variable: GDP			

The above results show both independent variables: COVID-19 (x) and lockdown and border closure (D) having a negative relationship with GDP. It means COVID-19 having a negative

impact on GDP and anti-COVID-19 policy has also the side effect of contraction shock to GDP by making zero trade openness and zero mobility of goods and services flow. The level of the negative impact of anti-COVID-19 policy: lockdown and border closure are more than COVID-19. It is anti-COVID-19 policy has negatively contributed 0.86% to 1% marginal change of GDP but COVID-19 j has only 0.44% to 1% marginal change of GDP. Therefore, the anti-COVID-19 policy was disastrous to the trade of Nepal.

Result IV: COVID-19 Pandemic, Trade, and Compensatory Policy Measures

In the above empirical results, COVID-19 pandemic and anti-COVID-19 policy were significantly negative to GDP or sector economy of Nepal, particularly trade sector by zero trade openness and zero goods and services flows over 7 months (March to September 2020). ADB (2020), IMF (2020), and World Bank (2020) projected its side effect as a contraction with 3% negative economic growth towards economic recession. During the COVID-19 pandemic, the economy had a big pressure of stabilizing growth and stimulating the threat of GDP loss and contraction. Therefore, the government of Nepal formulated a compensatory policy as follows:

Policy Shock I: Disclosure of Transportation Policy under which emergency and essential goods vehicles and markets were opened up and odd and even number system was made effective to private and public vehicles (MoHA, 2020). Similarly, import and export trade of food and medicine were opened up and human mobility was restrictively permitted.

Policy Shock II: Fiscal and Budgetary Policy were made compensatory in the national budget of Nepal 2020-2021 (MoF, 2020). In the budget, the government proposed the compensatory policy as follows: a) compensating to the poor and marginalized

people in public utility, b) rescheduling tax payment to trade, business, and industries, c) compensating to small and micro enterprises with a tax cut, d) proposal for Stimulus Package to the Business sector: i) allocation of Rs. 6 billion on medicine supply and management, ii) compensation to the poor and marginal people by free electricity to 10 units electricity consumer groups, 25% exemption to up to 150-unit electricity consumer groups, 50% exemption to up to 250-unit electricity consumer groups, free water bill, Rs. 100 billion. fund for tourism sector's rehabilitation and recovery, Rs. 100000 insurance to all health workers, the full exemption to airlines on their rent, exemption of renewal charge to communication and film industry, and Rs. 50 billion funds for new innovative projects and programs, e) tax exemption to comparative advantage able export items, f) expanding integrated custom office in all custom points, g) development and operation of dry ports in Indo-Nepal and China-Nepal border, h) review Indo-Nepal and Nepal-China Trade and Transit Treaty, i) exemption of Income-tax on Small and Micro_Enterprises for seven years -75% income tax exemption to less than Rs.2 million investment, 50% income tax exemption to Rs. 2-5 million investment, 25% income tax exemption to Rs. 5-10 million investments, j) removing Value Added Tax (VAT) on microinsurance, k) reducing custom duties on the import of agricultural products, l) 20% income tax exemption to tourism transport, m) custom duties exemption to medicines, including homeopathy medicine and n) 50 % income tax exemption to internet service.

Policy Shock III: Monetary Policy 2020-2021 was disclosed by the Central Bank of Nepal, Nepal Rashtriya Bank (NRB, 2020). The policy carries the compensatory policy as follows: a) compensatory through Rehabilitation, Recovery and Rescheduling Fund, b) rescheduling credit's principal and interest payment, c) refinancing to the vulnerable enterprises and industries through the Fund, d) special interest rate to the

vulnerable enterprises and industries, e) lower interest rate to the small and micro enterprises, f) management to liquidity, g) merging banks and financial institutions, h) establishing Hedging fund, i) 15% credit on priority sector – agriculture, energy, tourism and small and micro enterprise, j) facilitate credit to agricultural projects and small and micro enterprises at 5% interest rate, k) five times refinancing to the available refinancing fund, l) credit at 3% to export-oriented and vulnerable industries and enterprises, m) credit at 5% to small and micro enterprises and n) establishing Rs.50 billion NRs for credit rescheduling and refinancing.

Despite the compensatory policy, there would be issues as follows: a) no execution of above these policies and budget in the lockdown time and uncertainty of recovery, rehabilitation, and stimulus. Therefore, there was a curiosity about whether these policy shocks would be effective.

Conclusion

This paper analyzes the impact of COVID-19, anti-COVID-19 policy, and compensatory policy on the trade of Nepal based on secondary data through descriptive statistics and regression model tools. As a result, COVID-19 infected 44.8 million population and killed 1.2 million people of 215 countries of the world, where its extreme intensity felt in the US and G20 countries and India in South Asia and Brazil in South America. Subsequently, its economic consequence is a loss of 3.4% economic growth rate, worst stock market crash, loss of 400 million full-time jobs, and US\$ 3.5 trillion GDP loss (IMF, 2020 & UN, 2020).

Similarly, in SAARC, Nepal ranks fourth jumping at 35th of 215 countries of the World with 0.165 million affected people, 887 death tolls, per day new cases greater than 3000, and recovery rate greater than 74%. Furthermore, the empirical result is the negative impact of COVID-19 and anti-COVID-19 policy on the national economy, particularly trade. Anti-COVID-19 policy's

impact (0.86) is more severe than COVID-19 (0.44) in the economy. Its output is most vulnerable to trade: Indo-Nepal and SinoNepal.

Its outcomes are mixed: negative to sector economy, employment, and economic growth and positive to a trade deficit, trade dependency, and BOP. The compensatory policy is a stable shock to the negative consequence of COVID-19 and anti-COVID-19 policy. Therefore, Nepal is vulnerable to COVID-19, and the trade sector is the most vulnerable. For survival, stable and stimulus of national economy and trade, the compensatory policy should be implemented and anti-COVID-19 policy should be revised.

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